

Myth: AI will end discrimination

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As an allegedly objective state-of-the-art technology, there are hopes that AI may overcome human weaknesses. Some people believe that AI might be able to gain privileged access to knowledge, free of human biases and errors and thus end discrimination by realizing all in all fair and objective decisions.

We approach the de-mystification of this claim by looking at concrete examples of how AI (re)produces inequalities and connect those to several aspects which help to illustrate socio-technical entanglements. Drawing on a range of critical scholars, we argue that this simplifying myth might even be dangerous and point out what to do about it.

Myth

AI will end discrimination (or is at least less discriminatory than fallible and unfair human beings).

As part of society, AI is deeply rooted in it and as such not separable from structures of discrimination. Due to this socio-technical embeddedness, AI cannot make discrimination disappear by itself.

Material

Presentation slides

CORE READINGS

Benjamin, R. (2019a): *Captivating Technology. Race, Carceral Technoscience, and Liberatory Imagination in Everyday Life*. Durham: Duke University Press.

Benjamin, R. (2019b): *Race after technology: abolitionist tools for the new Jim code*. Cambridge: UKPolity.

Criado-Perez, C. (2020): *Unsichtbare Frauen. Wie eine von Daten beherrschte Welt die Hälfte der Bevölkerung ignoriert*. München: btb Verlag.

D'Ignazio, C.; Klein, L. F. (2020): *Data Feminism*. Strong ideas series Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England: The MIT Press.

Buolamwini, J.; Gebru, T. (2018): Gender Shades: Intersectional Accuracy Disparities in Commercial Gender Classification. In: *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research 81*. Paper präsentiert bei der Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency, 1–15.

ADDITIONAL READINGS

Eubanks, V. (2017): *Automating inequality. How high-tech tools profile, police, and punish the poor*. First Edition. New York, NY: St. Martin's Press

O'Neil, C. (2016): *Weapons of math destruction. How big data increases inequality and threatens democracy*. First edition. New York: Crown.

Zuboff, S. (2020): *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism. The Fight for a Human Future at the new Frontier of Power*. First Trade Paperback Edition. New York: PublicAffairs.

Cave, S.; Dihal, K. (2020): The Whiteness of AI. In: *Philosophy & Technology* 33(4), 685–703.

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Why, AI?

This post is part of our project “Why, AI?”. It is a learning space which helps you to find out more about the myths and truths surrounding automation, algorithms, society and ourselves. It is continuously being filled with new contributions.